

ANALYSIS, CONTROL AND SYNCHRONIZATION OF SPROTT-K SYSTEM WITH UNKNOWN PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the problem of designing an adaptive controller and synchronizer for the new Sprott-K chaotic system (1994), when the system parameters are unknown. Sprott-K system is one of the important models of 3-dimensional chaotic systems. First, we construct an adaptive controller to stabilize the Sprott-K chaotic system to its unstable equilibrium at the origin. Then we construct an adaptive synchronizer to achieve global chaos synchronization of the identical Sprott-K chaotic systems with unknown parameters. Lyapunov stability theory and the adaptive control theory have been applied to prove all the control and synchronization results derived in this paper. Numerical simulations have been presented to illustrate the main results for the Sprott-K chaotic system.

KEYWORDS

Adaptive Control, Chaos, Chaotic Systems, Synchronization, Sprott-K System.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chaotic systems are nonlinear dynamical systems characterized by the *butterfly effect*, viz. systems, which are extremely sensitive to tiny changes in initial conditions. The first known chaotic system was discovered by Lorenz ([1], 1963) while he was simulating weather models. A chaotic system simpler than the Lorenz system was proposed by Rössler ([2], 1976). The theoretical equations of the Rössler system were later found to be useful in modelling equilibrium in chemical reactions.

The control of chaotic systems is to design state feedback control laws that stabilizes the chaotic systems around the unstable equilibrium points. Active control technique is used when the system parameters are known and adaptive control technique is used when the system parameters are unknown [3-4].

The synchronization of chaotic systems is a phenomenon that may occur when two or more chaotic attractors are coupled or when a chaotic attractor drives another chaotic attractor. In the last two decades, there has been significant interest in the literature on the synchronization of chaotic and hyperchaotic systems [5-16].

In 1990, Pecora and Carroll [5] introduced a method to synchronize two identical chaotic systems and showed that it was possible for some chaotic systems to be completely synchronized. From then on, chaos synchronization has been widely explored in a variety of fields including physical systems [6], chemical systems [7], ecological systems [8], secure communications [9-10], etc.

The seminal work by Pecora and Carroll (1990) has been followed by a variety of impressive approaches in the literature such as the sampled-data feedback method [11], OGY method [12], time-delay feedback method [13], backstepping method [14], active control method [15-20], adaptive control method [21-25], sliding mode control method [26-28], etc.

This paper derives new results for the design of adaptive control and synchronization of the Sprott-K chaotic system ([29], 1994), which is one of the paradigms of 3-D chaotic systems, when the system parameters are known. Lyapunov stability theory and adaptive control theory have been used to derive the main results of this paper.

2. ANALYSIS OF SPROTT-K SYSTEM

The Sprott-K system (1994) is described by the 3D dynamics

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1 &= x_1x_2 - ax_3 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= x_1 - bx_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_1 + cx_3\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where x_1, x_2, x_3 are the state variables of the system and a, b, c are constant, positive parameters of the system.

The system (1) is chaotic when the parameter values are taken as

$$a = 1, b = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad c = 0.3\tag{2}$$

Figure 1 describes the strange attractor of the Sprott-K chaotic system (1).

Figure 1. The Strange Attractor of the Sprott-K Chaotic System

When the parameter values are taken as in (2) for the Sprott-K chaotic system (1), the system linearization matrix at the equilibrium point $E_0 = (0,0,0)$ is given by

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix}$$

which has the eigenvalues

$$\lambda_1 = 0.1500 + 0.9887 i, \quad \lambda_2 = 0.1500 - 0.9887 i \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_3 = -1$$

Since λ_1 and λ_2 are unstable eigenvalues of A , it follows from Lyapunov stability theory [30] that the Sprott-K system (1) is unstable at the equilibrium point $E_0 = (0,0,0)$.

3. ADAPTIVE CONTROL OF THE SPROTT-K CHAOTIC SYSTEM

3.1 Theoretical Results

In this section, we design adaptive control law for globally stabilizing the Sprott-K system (1994), when the parameter values are unknown.

Thus, we consider the controlled Sprott-K system, which is described by the 3D dynamics

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1 &= x_1 x_2 - a x_3 + u_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= x_1 - b x_2 + u_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_1 + c x_3 + u_3\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

where u_1, u_2 and u_3 are feedback controllers to be designed using the states x_1, x_2, x_3 and estimates $\hat{a}, \hat{b}, \hat{c}$ of the unknown parameters a, b, c of the system.

In order to ensure that the controlled system (3) globally converges to the origin asymptotically, we consider the following adaptive control functions

$$\begin{aligned}u_1 &= -x_1 x_2 + \hat{a} x_3 - k_1 x_1 \\ u_2 &= -x_1 + \hat{b} x_2 - k_2 x_2 \\ u_3 &= -x_1 - \hat{c} x_3 - k_3 x_3\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

where \hat{a}, \hat{b} and \hat{c} are estimates of the parameters a, b and c , respectively, and $k_i, (i=1, 2, 3)$ are positive constants.

Substituting the control law (4) into the controlled Sprott-K dynamics (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1 &= -(a - \hat{a}) x_3 - k_1 x_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= -(b - \hat{b}) x_2 - k_2 x_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= (c - \hat{c}) x_3 - k_3 x_3\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

Let us now define the parameter errors as

$$\begin{aligned}e_a &= a - \hat{a} \\ e_b &= b - \hat{b} \\ e_c &= c - \hat{c}\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

Using (6), the closed-loop dynamics (5) can be written compactly as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1 &= -e_a x_3 - k_1 x_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= -e_b x_2 - k_2 x_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= e_c x_3 - k_3 x_3\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

For the derivation of the update law for adjusting the parameter estimates \hat{a}, \hat{b} and \hat{c} , the Lyapunov approach is used.

Consider the quadratic Lyapunov function

$$V(x_1, x_2, x_3, e_a, e_b, e_c) = \frac{1}{2} (x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + e_a^2 + e_b^2 + e_c^2)\tag{8}$$

which is a positive definite function on R^6 .

Note also that

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{e}_a &= -\hat{a} \\ \dot{e}_b &= -\hat{b} \\ \dot{e}_c &= -\hat{c}\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

Differentiating V along the trajectories of (7) and using (9), we obtain

$$\dot{V} = -k_1 x_1^2 - k_2 x_2^2 - k_3 x_3^2 + e_a (-x_1 x_3 - \hat{a}) + e_b (-x_2^2 - \hat{b}) + e_c (x_3^2 - \hat{c})\tag{10}$$

In view of Eq. (10), the estimated parameters are updated by the following law:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\hat{a}} &= -x_1 x_3 + k_4 e_a \\ \dot{\hat{b}} &= -x_2^2 + k_5 e_b \\ \dot{\hat{c}} &= x_3^2 + k_6 e_c\end{aligned}\tag{11}$$

where k_4, k_5 and k_6 are positive constants.

Next, we prove the following result.

Theorem 1. *The controlled Sprott-K system (1) with unknown parameters is globally and exponentially stabilized for all initial conditions $x(0) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ by the adaptive control law (4), where the update law for the parameters is given by (11) and $k_i, (i = 1, \dots, 6)$ are positive constants.*

Proof. Substituting (11) into (10), we get

$$\dot{V} = -k_1 x_1^2 - k_2 x_2^2 - k_3 x_3^2 - k_4 e_a^2 - k_5 e_b^2 - k_6 e_c^2\tag{12}$$

which is a negative definite function on \mathbb{R}^6 .

Thus, by Lyapunov stability theory [30], it is immediate that the controlled Sprott-K system (7) is globally exponentially stable and also that the parameter estimation errors e_a, e_b, e_c exponentially converge to zero with time.

This completes the proof. ■

3.2 Numerical Results

For the numerical simulations, the fourth order Runge-Kutta method with time-step $h = 10^{-8}$ is used to solve the system (3) with the adaptive control law (4) and parameter update law (11).

The parameters of the Sprott-K system (3) are selected as

$$a = 1, \quad b = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad c = 0.3$$

For the adaptive and update laws, we take

$$k_i = 4, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, 6).$$

Suppose that the initial values of the estimated parameters are

$$\hat{a}(0) = 6, \hat{b}(0) = 14, \hat{c}(0) = 16$$

The initial state of the controlled Sprott-K system (3) is taken as

$$x_1(0) = 9, x_2(0) = -4, x_3(0) = 10$$

When the adaptive control law (4) and the parameter update law (11) are used, the controlled modified Sprott-K system converges to the equilibrium $E_0 = (0,0,0)$ exponentially as shown in Figure 2.

The time-history of the parameter estimates is shown in Figure 3.

The time-history of the parameter estimation errors is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2. Time Responses of the Controlled Sprott-K System

Figure 3. Time-History of the Parameter Estimates $\hat{a}(t)$, $\hat{b}(t)$, $\hat{c}(t)$

Figure 4. Time-History of the Parameter Estimates e_a, e_b, e_c

4. ADAPTIVE SYNCHRONIZATION OF IDENTICAL SPROTT-K SYSTEMS

4.1 Theoretical Results

In this section, we discuss the adaptive synchronization of identical Sprott-K chaotic systems (1994) with unknown parameters.

As the master system, we consider the Sprott-K dynamics described by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1 &= x_1x_2 - ax_3 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= x_1 - bx_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_1 + cx_3\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

where x_i , ($i=1,2,3$) are the state variables and a, b, c are unknown system parameters.

As the slave system, we consider the controlled Sprott-K system described by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{y}_1 &= y_1y_2 - ay_3 + u_1 \\ \dot{y}_2 &= y_1 - by_2 + u_2 \\ \dot{y}_3 &= y_1 + cy_3 + u_3\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

where y_i , ($i=1,2,3$) are the state variables and u_i , ($i=1,2,3$) are adaptive controllers to be designed.

The synchronization error is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}e_1 &= y_1 - x_1 \\ e_2 &= y_2 - x_2 \\ e_3 &= y_3 - x_3\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

Then the error dynamics is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{e}_1 &= -ae_3 + y_1y_2 - x_1x_2 + u_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 &= e_1 - be_2 + u_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 &= e_1 + ce_3 + u_3\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

Let us now define the adaptive control functions $u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t)$ as

$$\begin{aligned}u_1 &= \hat{a}e_3 - y_1y_2 + x_1x_2 - k_1e_1 \\ u_2 &= -e_1 + \hat{b}e_2 - k_2e_2 \\ u_3 &= -e_1 - \hat{c}e_3 - k_3e_3\end{aligned}\tag{17}$$

where \hat{a}, \hat{b} and \hat{c} are estimates of the parameters a, b and c , respectively, and $k_i, (i=1,2,3)$ are positive constants.

Substituting the control law (17) into (16), we obtain the error dynamics as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{e}_1 &= -(a - \hat{a})e_3 - k_1e_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 &= -(b - \hat{b})e_2 - k_2e_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 &= (c - \hat{c})e_3 - k_3e_3\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

Let us now define the parameter errors as

$$\begin{aligned}e_a &= a - \hat{a} \\ e_b &= b - \hat{b} \\ e_c &= c - \hat{c}\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

Substituting (19) into (18), the error dynamics simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{e}_1 &= -e_ae_3 - k_1e_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 &= -e_be_2 - k_2e_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 &= e_ce_3 - k_3e_3\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

Consider the quadratic Lyapunov function

$$V(e_1, e_2, e_3, e_a, e_b, e_c) = \frac{1}{2}(e_1^2 + e_2^2 + e_3^2 + e_a^2 + e_b^2 + e_c^2)\quad (21)$$

Clearly, V is a positive definite function on R^6 .
Note also that

$$\dot{e}_a = -\dot{\hat{a}}, \quad \dot{e}_b = -\dot{\hat{b}}, \quad \dot{e}_c = -\dot{\hat{c}}\quad (22)$$

Differentiating V along the trajectories of (20) and using (22), we obtain

$$\dot{V} = -k_1e_1^2 - k_2e_2^2 - k_3e_3^2 + e_a(-e_1e_3 - \dot{\hat{a}}) + e_b(-e_2^2 - \dot{\hat{b}}) + e_c(e_3^2 - \dot{\hat{c}})\quad (23)$$

In view of Eq. (23), the estimated parameters are updated by the following law:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\hat{a}} &= -e_1e_3 + k_4e_a \\ \dot{\hat{b}} &= -e_2^2 + k_5e_b \\ \dot{\hat{c}} &= e_3^2 + k_6e_c\end{aligned}\quad (24)$$

where k_4, k_5 and k_6 are positive constants.

Theorem 2. *The identical Sprott-K systems (13) and (14) with unknown parameters are globally and exponentially synchronized for all initial conditions by the adaptive control law (17), where the update law for parameters is given by (24) and $k_i, (i = 1, \dots, 6)$ are positive constants.*

Proof. Substituting (24) into (23), we get

$$\dot{V} = -k_1 e_1^2 - k_2 e_2^2 - k_3 e_3^2 - k_4 e_a^2 - k_5 e_b^2 - k_6 e_c^2 \quad (25)$$

From (25), we find that \dot{V} is a negative definite function on R^6 .

Thus, by Lyapunov stability theory [30], it is immediate that the synchronization error and the parameter error decay to zero exponentially with time for all initial conditions. ■

4.2 Numerical Results

For the numerical simulations, the fourth order Runge-Kutta method with time-step $h = 10^{-8}$ is used to solve the two systems of differential equations (13) and (14) with the adaptive control law (17) and the parameter update law (24).

We take the parameter values as in the chaotic case, viz.

$$a = 1, b = 1 \text{ and } c = 0.3.$$

We take the positive constants

$$k_i, (i = 1, \dots, 8) \text{ as } k_i = 4 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, 6.$$

Suppose that the initial values of the estimated parameters are

$$\hat{a}(0) = 6, \hat{b}(0) = 12, \hat{c}(0) = 5$$

We take the initial values of the master system (13) as

$$x_1(0) = 8, x_2(0) = -17, x_3(0) = 4$$

We take the initial values of the slave system (14) as

$$y_1(0) = 10, y_2(0) = 2, y_3(0) = -7$$

Figure 5 shows the complete synchronization of the identical Sprott-K systems.

Figure 6 shows the time-history of the synchronization error e_1, e_2, e_3 .

Figure 7 shows the time-history of the parameter estimates $\hat{a}(t), \hat{b}(t), \hat{c}(t)$.

Figure 8 shows the time-history of the parameter estimation errors e_a, e_b, e_c .

Figure 5. Complete Synchronization of Identical Sprott-K Systems

Figure 6. Time History of the Synchronization Error e_1, e_2, e_3

Figure 7. Time-History of the Parameter Estimates $\hat{a}(t), \hat{b}(t), \hat{c}(t)$

Figure 8. Time-History of the Parameter Estimation Error e_a, e_b, e_c

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we applied adaptive control theory for the stabilization and synchronization of the Sprott-K system (1994) with unknown system parameters. First, we designed adaptive control laws to stabilize the Sprott-K system to its unstable equilibrium point at the origin based on the adaptive control theory and Lyapunov stability theory. Then we derived adaptive synchronization scheme and update law for the estimation of system parameters for the identical Sprott-K systems with unknown parameters. Our synchronization schemes were established using Lyapunov stability theory. Since the Lyapunov exponents are not required for these calculations, the proposed adaptive control method is very effective and convenient to achieve chaos control and synchronization of the Sprott-K chaotic system. Numerical simulations are shown to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed adaptive stabilization and synchronization schemes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lorenz, E.N. (1963) "Deterministic nonperiodic flow," *J. Atmos. Phys.* Vol. 20, pp 131-141.
- [2] Rössler, O.E. (1976) "An equation for continuous chaos," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 57, pp 397-398.
- [3] Wang, X., Tian, L. & Yu, L. (2006) "Adaptive control and slow manifold analysis of a new chaotic system," *Internat. J. Nonlinear Science*, Vol. 21, pp 43-49.
- [4] Sun, M., Tian, L., Jiang, S. & Xun, J. (2007) "Feedback control and adaptive control of the energy resource chaotic system," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 32, pp 168-180.
- [5] Pecora, L.M. & Carroll, T.L. (1990) "Synchronization in chaotic systems", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 64, pp 821-824.
- [6] Lakshmanan, M. & Murali, K. (1996) *Nonlinear Oscillators: Controlling and Synchronization*, World Scientific, Singapore.
- [7] Han, S.K., Kerrer, C. & Kuramoto, Y. (1995) "Dephasing and bursting in coupled neural oscillators", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 75, pp 3190-3193.
- [8] Blasius, B., Huppert, A. & Stone, L. (1999) "Complex dynamics and phase synchronization in spatially extended ecological system", *Nature*, Vol. 399, pp 354-359.
- [9] Feki, M. (2003) "An adaptive chaos synchronization scheme applied to secure communication", *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Vol. 18, pp 141-148.
- [10] Murali, K. & Lakshmanan, M. (1998) "Secure communication using a compound signal from generalized synchronizable chaotic systems", *Phys. Rev. Lett. A*, Vol. 241, pp 303-310.
- [11] Yang, T. & Chua, L.O. (1999) "Control of chaos using sampled-data feedback control", *Internat. J. Bifurcat. Chaos*, Vol. 9, pp 215-219.
- [12] Ott, E., Grebogi, C. & Yorke, J.A. (1990) "Controlling chaos", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 64, pp 1196-1199.
- [13] Park, J.H. & Kwon, O.M. (2003) "A novel criterion for delayed feedback control of time-delay chaotic systems", *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Vol. 17, pp 709-716.
- [14] Yu, Y.G. & Zhang, S.C. (2006) "Adaptive backstepping synchronization of uncertain chaotic systems", *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Vol. 27, pp 1369-1375.
- [15] Ho, M.C. & Hung, Y.C. (2002) "Synchronization of two different chaotic systems by using generalized active control", *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 301, pp 424-428.
- [16] Huang, L., Feng, R. & Wang, M. (2004) "Synchronization of chaotic systems via nonlinear control", *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 320, pp 271-275.
- [17] Tang, R.A., Liu, Y.L. & Xue, J.K. (2009) "An extended active control for chaos synchronization," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 373, No. 6, pp 1449-1454.

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- [18] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Output regulation of the Sprott-G chaotic system by state feedback control", *International Journal of Instrumentation and Control Systems*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp 20-30.
- [19] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Global chaos synchronization of Lorenz and Pehlivan chaotic systems by nonlinear control", *International Journal of Advances in Science and Technology*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp 19-28.
- [20] Lei, Y., Xu, W. & Zheng, H. (2005) "Synchronization of two chaotic nonlinear gyros using active control," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 343, No. 1, pp 153-158.
- [21] Liao, T.L. & Tsai, S.H. (2000) "Adaptive synchronization of chaotic systems and its applications to secure communications", *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Vol. 11, pp 1387-1396.
- [22] Park, J.H., Lee, S.M. & Kwon, O.M. (2007) "Adaptive synchronization of Genesio-Tesi chaotic system via a novel feedback control," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 371, pp 263-270.
- [23] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Adaptive control and synchronization of hyperchaotic Chen system", *International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services*, Vol. 1, No. 3, pp 22-33.
- [24] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Adaptive synchronization of hyperchaotic Lorenz and hyperchaotic Lü systems", *International Journal of Instrumentation and Control Systems*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp 1-18.
- [25] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Adaptive control and synchronization of hyperchaotic Cai system", *International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modeling*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp 1-13.
- [26] Konishi, K., Hirai, M. & Kokame, H. (1998) "Sliding mode control for a class of chaotic systems", *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 245, pp 511-517.
- [27] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Sliding mode controller design for synchronization of Shimizu-Morioka chaotic system", *International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp 20-29.
- [28] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Global chaos synchronization of four-wing chaotic systems by sliding mode control", *International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modeling*, Vol., 1 No. 1, pp 15-31.
- [29] Sprott, J.C. (1994) "Some simple chaotic flows," *Physical Review E*, Vol. 50, No. 2, pp. 647-650.
- [30] Hahn, W. (1967) *The Stability of Motion*, Springer, New York.

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